

Kinetic Study of the Silver Oxide Decomposed Product of Ethereal Blue Perchromate

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The kinetics of the reaction between decomposition products of ethereal blue perchromate (obtained in presence and absence of silver oxide) and oxalic acid has been studied. The total order of the reaction has been calculated and mechanism suggested.

Ethereal blue perchromate is quite unstable.¹ Its constitution has been studied in two ways, (a) by following the reaction between potassium dichromate and hydrogen peroxide²⁻⁵ and (b) by studying the nature of its stable decomposition products and then extrapolating the results so obtained⁶⁻⁹. In the latter way R. Schwarz and H. Giese observed the formation of chromic acid on decomposing the blue perchromate in presence of silver oxide which led them to propose CrO_5 formula to the blue perchromate.

Rai⁷ and Rai & coworkers⁸ observed the formation of $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3$ in presence of water which according to them can be explained only by accepting $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_3$ formula for the blue perchromate and not by CrO_5 . They have further shown⁹ that contrary to Schwarz and Giese's contention the silver oxide itself participates in the above decomposition leading to the formation of chromic acid.

The present paper deals with an additional support to the view that silver oxide plays oxidising role during the decomposition of blue perchromate by studying the kinetics of the reaction between oxalic acid and (i) the above decomposition products (obtained in presence and absence of silver oxide), (ii) the effluent obtained by exchanging the products with a cation exchanger and (iii) chromic acid.

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E X P E R I M E N T A L

Chemicals used during the course of the work were A. R., B. D. H. and the solutions were prepared in double distilled water.

The ethereal blue perchromate and its decomposition product in water were prepared as described earlier (loc. cit.). Its decomposition product in presence of silver oxide was prepared as:—

Fifty millilitres of the ethereal blue perchromate was allowed to decompose in a conical flask having about 15 gms. of pure and dried silver oxide. The decomposition was complete in a few minutes leaving a brown mass and upper ethereal layer. The ether was decanted off and the brown mass was treated with dil. hydrochloric acid and filtered. The filtrate was collected and named as the decomposition product of blue perchromate in presence of silver oxide.

Exchanged Solutions:—The decomposition products obtained in presence of water and silver oxide were allowed to trickle through a cation exchanger [Amberlite IR-120 (H)] and the effluents obtained were collected. These were named as E₁ and E₂ solutions.

Chromic Acid:—N/100 Chromic acid solution was prepared by dissolving the required quantity in the distilled water.

The following readings were taken with the above solutions before proceeding with the kinetic studies:—

(a) Ten millilitres of all the solutions were titrated iodometrically against a standard N/50 thiosulphate solution.

(b) Ten millilitres of all the above solutions were separately treated with 5 ml. of 30% H₂O₂ in alkaline medium (NaOH). The solutions were then boiled for about 45 minutes to boil off excess of peroxide and then titrated iodometrically against the same thiosulphate solution.

Kinetic Study:—The solutions of oxalic acid and the decomposition product prepared in water were placed in a bath maintained at the desired temperature within the range of $\pm 0.5^\circ$. After some time both the solutions were rapidly mixed and the stop watch was started when half of the oxalic acid solution was added. Aliquots of the reaction mixture were withdrawn at definite intervals of time and the amount of unconsumed decomposition product was determined by titrating the reaction mixture iodometrically against standard N/250 thiosulphate solution. Similar studies were made with the decomposition product prepared in Ag₂O, exchanged solutions E₁ and E₂ and chromic acid solution. The calculated first order rate constants were found to be fairly satisfactory and the results were quite reproducible. The order of the reaction was determined by Ostwald's Isolation Method¹⁰.

Effect of Oxalic acid concentration:—To determine the total order of the

reaction for different cases, the effect of different concentrations of oxalic acid (much higher than that of other solution) was studied. The results are recorded in table II.

Effect of Temperature :—The effect of temperature on the rate constants of the reactions was studied and the results noted in table II.

Physical Constants :—Calculated values for the temperature co-efficients and energy of activation are recorded in table IV.

Observations noted in table I show that the water decomposition product contains Cr (III) which gets oxidised to Cr(VI) on treatment with hydrogen peroxide. Constant titration values in other cases show that there is no such Cr (III) available for oxidation.

TABLE I

Solution	Vol. of thiosulphate solution used in titrating		
	10 ml. of unoxidised solution	10 ml of oxidised solution	Ratio
	a	b	b/a
Dec. Pro. in water	6.50	8.80	1.35
Dec. Pro. in Silver oxide	6.35	6.40	1.00
Exchanged Solution E ₁ or E ₂	6.85	6.90	1.00
Chromic acid solution	5.00	5.00	1.00

TABLE II

Effect of Temperature and Concentration of Oxalic acid

Conc. of Oxalic acid	Temp. °C	Dec. Pro. in water K min ⁻¹	Dec. Pro. in Ag ₂ O K	Exchanged E ₁ or E ₂ K	Chromic acid K
N/10	25	0.005234	0.003528	0.003705	0.003491
	30	0.006664	0.005366	0.006028	0.005390
	35	0.008211	0.006849	0.007783	0.006929
N/8	25	0.009053	0.006381	0.007070	0.006214
	30	0.011050	0.009099	0.010330	0.008824
	35	0.014130	0.013110	0.013900	0.011650
N/5	25	0.024960	0.020820	0.021200	0.020480
	30	0.031770	0.027330	0.024530	0.024830
	35	0.043570	0.038410	0.036500	0.035130

TABLE III

Order of the Reaction with respect to Oxalic acid

Dec. Pro. in water	Dec. Pro. in Ag ₂ O	Exchanged Pro. E ₁ or E ₂	Chromic acid
2.258	2.596	2.879	2.743
2.132	2.817	2.670	2.735
2.280	2.746	2.881	2.738
2.048	2.623	3.107	
i.e.2	i.e.3	i. e. 3	i.e.3
<i>Total Order of the Reaction</i>			
1+2=3	1+3=4	1+3=4	1+3=4

TABLE IV

PHYSICAL CONSTANTS

N/10 Oxalic acid and N/200 Decomposition product in water, Decomposition product in Ag₂O, Exchanged E₁ and E₂ or Chromic acid.

Physical constant	Dec. Pro. in water	Dec. Pro. in Ag ₂ O	Exchanged E ₁ or E ₂	Chromic acid
<i>Energy of Activation</i>	Kcal.	Kcal.	Kcal.	Kcal.
1) Between				
25° & 30°	8.676	15.05	17.47	15.60
2) Between				
25° & 35°	8.215	12.11	13.54	12.51
<i>Temperature Coefficient</i>				
1) Between				
25° & 30°	1.274	1.522	1.628	1.545
2) Between				
25° & 35°	1.569	1.942	2.101	1.986

DISCUSSION

The ratio b/a in table I shows that there is increase in titration value on oxidising the water decomposition product. This increase has been explained on the basis of Cr (III) present in the product being converted to Cr (VI). Other products show no increase as they contain only hexavalent chromium.

Dhar¹¹ has shown the reaction between chromic acid and oxalic acid to be one with respect to chromic acid and three with respect to oxalic acid i.e. total order

$1 + 3 = 4$. Values of the velocity constant (k) recorded in table II are for the same¹¹ concentration of reactants and are fairly constant for an unimolecular reaction and thus the value of m i.e. order with respect to oxidant (water decomposition product, product in silver oxide, exchanged solution or chromic acid) will be one. The value of n i.e. the order with respect to oxalic acid is three in each case except for water decomposition product when it is 2. The total order of the reaction i.e. $m+n$ has thus been found to be $1 + 3 = 4$ in each case except for the reaction between water decomposition product and oxalic acid, when it is $1 + 2 = 3$.

These observations thus support the previous result that decomposition product in presence of silver oxide is chromic acid. The product is different in absence of silver oxide as shown by the change of total order from 4 to 3.

The lowering of the total order of reaction in case of water decomposition product seems to be due to the presence of trivalent chromium which has been shown to be present in it along with chromium (VI). This may be explained as:

(1) In case of oxalic acid and chromic acid, exchanged product formed in presence of silver oxide.

(2) In case of oxalic acid and water decomposition product or product formed in absence of silver oxide.

Workers^{8,9} have assigned $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3$ formula to the water decomposition product.

Stabilising of pentavalent chromium by complex formation has been suggested by several workers^{12,13}. The third atom of oxygen which is utilised for the oxidation

12. K. B. Wiberg and W. H. Richardson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 2800,

13. F. H. Westheimer, *Chemical Review*, 1949, 448.

of one more molecule of oxalic acid, in case of chromic acid is used up in this case for the oxidation of Cr (III) to Cr (V) state which in turn is stabilised by complex formation. The total order of the reaction, therefore, in case of water decomposition product will be three and not four as in case of chromic acid.

The earlier observations of the author (loc. cit.) regarding the presence of trivalent chromium along with hexavalent in decomposition products in absence of silver oxide and that of several workers ¹⁴⁻¹⁶ regarding the quantitative oxidation of Cr (III) to Cr (VI) by Ag_2O thus when taken together make it clear that silver oxide if present during the decomposition of blue perchromate oxidises the otherwise present trivalent chromium to hexavalent state (table I).

Physical constant data tabulated in table IV also confirm that the product in presence of silver oxide is chromic acid and different from the one prepared in absence of silver oxide.

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Received October 4, 1967,
Revised MSS. received January, 8, 1969.

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